

AQUASERV

Research services
for **sustainable aquaculture,**
fisheries and blue economy

D7.3 Challenge-driven call

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1. Executive Summary

AQUASERV aims to provide remote or on-site access to research infrastructures in areas related to marine and freshwater biological resources, aquaculture, fisheries, and biotechnology in response to European strategies for developing a blue economy. There are two types of access calls: one is permanently open and encompasses all the domains covered by AQUASERV, while the other is challenge-driven and addresses specific European challenges/policies. Position papers and policy briefs produced by think tanks, such as the Marine Board and Joint Programming Initiative Healthy and Productive Seas and Oceans, were consulted to define the content addressed by the challenge-driven calls. The Executive Committee approved the following roadmap for the challenge-driven calls:

1. Ecological Restoration, May 2025
2. Sustainable Aquaculture, December 2025
3. Sustainable Fisheries, August 2026
4. Blue Biotechnology, April 2027
5. All topics, December 2027.

2. Background / Introduction

AQUASERV was established to directly contribute to the system-based changes identified as essential by the EU to drive policy and socioeconomic performance, as outlined in the European Green Deal¹, Farm to Fork Strategy² and the Common Fisheries Policy³, the Sustainable Blue Economy⁴, and the Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters 2030"⁵. This is to be achieved through the provision of on-site or remote transnational (TA) and/or virtual access (VA) from a catalogue of customised services combining workflows of scientific services from multiple research infrastructures (RIs), including training, and with an ambitious outreach programme and engagement plan directed at research communities from the public and private sector. AQUASERV initiated TA in November 2024 with a continuous open call aimed at advancing frontier knowledge across all fields covered by AQUASERV, with awards issued every four months. In parallel, AQUASERV will organise regular challenge-driven TA calls open to academics and industry for access to integrated and customised RI services that contribute to advancing EU policies and Horizon missions, as indicated above. The call priorities were defined with documents produced by think tanks such as the European Marine Board and the Joint Programming Initiative Healthy and Productive Seas and Oceans (JPI Oceans). To support the TA offer, particularly the challenge-driven calls, AQUASERV will develop multidisciplinary or synergistic, customised services to be deployed during the project through internal calls for joint research.

3. Description of work

The challenge-driven calls seek to accelerate the pace of the research cycle and enhance the delivery of solutions to European challenges and priorities by providing customised research infrastructure services to facilitate the transition toward a sustainable Europe and a prosperous economy. The project coordination proposed the challenge-driven calls with the topics listed below, which were revised by the Scientific External Advisory Board and approved by the Executive Committee.

3.1. Promoting Ecological Restoration

Human activities and climate change are responsible for habitat destruction and biodiversity loss, leading to a decline in ecosystem services. The European Commission adopted the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) to maintain clean, healthy, productive, and resilient marine ecosystems while ensuring a more sustainable use of marine resources. Ecological restoration, "the process of assisting the recovery of an ecosystem that has been degraded, damaged, or destroyed," is an additional requirement to support ecosystems where natural recovery is hindered or impeded. Restoration, impact reduction, and rehabilitation are strategies to mitigate degradation and

¹ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

² https://food.ec.europa.eu/horizontal-topics/farm-fork-strategy_en

³ https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/policy/common-fisheries-policy-cfp_en

⁴ https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/ocean/blue-economy/sustainable-blue-economy_en

⁵ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/restore-our-ocean-and-waters_en

damage, which are crucial for preserving biodiversity. The Regulation on Nature Restoration (Nature Restoration Law)⁶ came into effect on August 18, 2024, setting binding targets to restore degraded ecosystems, particularly those with the greatest potential to capture and store carbon, while preventing and reducing the impact of natural disasters. As an overall target to be achieved at the EU level, Member States will implement restoration measures in at least 20% of their sea areas by 2030. One of the targets of the recently agreed Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework⁷ is to ensure that by 2030, at least 30% of degraded terrestrial, inland water, and marine and coastal ecosystems are under effective restoration. Contributing to the same objectives, the Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030 aims to protect and restore the health of our ocean and waters through research and innovation, citizen engagement, and blue investments.

To contribute to the objectives of the AQUASERV Ecosystem Restoration call, projects should address one or more of the following topics:

- Understanding of the factors that generate, maintain, and deplete biodiversity in marine environments;
- Understanding the effects of environmental stressors on marine biodiversity, and how species and populations may adapt to changing marine environments and the implications of such changes for ocean function and human well-being;
- The impacts of emerging and expanding human activities on marine biodiversity to ensure we have the knowledge to effectively manage such activities in the future;
- The spatio-temporal microbial distribution in marine ecosystems, and prediction of future epidemic risks from the spread of microbes introduced by invasive species, or from increased resistance to antibiotics used in fish farms;
- Evaluation of the epidemiological, genetic, and ecological consequences of invasive species, including assessing the risks to the native ecosystems, and studying the responses of invasive species to the present and future environmental conditions and drivers of change (e.g. climate and increasing human activities);
- Novel methodologies for ecological restoration, including improving cultivation, transport and transplantation, and measuring impacts;
- The use of Nature-based Solutions in mitigation processes;
- Understanding the link between marine biodiversity and essential ecosystem services of societal benefit;
- Translating the knowledge generated through biodiversity research in areas such as sustainable fisheries, aquaculture, marine biotechnology, and ecotourism;
- Contribution of Marine Protected Areas to ecological restoration;
- Other topics that can contribute to the European policies promoting ecological restoration.

3.2. Promoting Sustainable Aquaculture

The Farm to Fork Strategy is at the heart of the European Green Deal, aiming to make food systems fair, healthy, and environmentally friendly. The impact of multiple and cumulative human stressors is particularly relevant as human activities on the ocean will continue to increase under the European Commission's Blue Growth agenda and the increased need for food from the oceans (Scientific Advice Mechanism, 2017)⁸. With increased pressure on wild stocks, aquaculture has become critical for future food production. The European Marine Board (Position paper 20), the JPI Oceans Strategy Framework 2021-2025, and the Review of the Strategic Research Innovation Agenda from the European Aquaculture Technology Innovation Platform (2017)⁹ are aligned in their priorities, which have been included as part of the AQUASERV call. To contribute to the objectives of this call, projects should address one or more of the following topics:

- New low-trophic species for aquaculture;
- New and improved sustainable feed production technologies;
- Managing pathogens, parasites, and health risks in aquaculture;
- Quality and safety of aquaculture products;
- Managing aquaculture waste.
- Aquaculture sustainability topics that contribute to the Farm to Fork strategy.

3.3. Sustainable Fisheries

⁶ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/news/nature-restoration-law-enters-force-2024-08-15_en

⁷ <https://www.cbd.int/gbf>

⁸ <https://scientificadvice.eu/advice/food-from-the-oceans/>

⁹ <https://www.cbd.int/aichi-targets/target/11>

The Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) is a set of rules for sustainably managing European fishing fleets and conserving fish stocks and aims to increase productivity, stabilise markets, provide a source of healthy food and ensure reasonable prices for consumers. Fishing activities continue to adversely affect marine ecosystems, particularly through seabed disturbance, bycatch of sensitive species and effects on marine food webs. These effects are combined with those of climate change and other pressures from human activities. At the same time, the poor status of marine ecosystems is also a direct threat to the sustainability of fisheries, aquaculture, and their related economic activities, as well as to the well-being of communities dependent on them. The [Marine Action Plan \(MAP\)](#)⁷ adopted by the European Commission following COP15 and taking into consideration the [Biodiversity Strategy for 2030](#)⁸ aims to contribute to getting and keeping fish stocks to sustainable levels, reduce the impact of fishing on the seabed, and minimise fisheries' impacts on sensitive species. To contribute to the CFP and the MAP and the objectives of the AQUASERV Sustainable Fisheries call, projects should address one or more of the following topics:

- Selectivity of fishing gear;
- Reducing and managing fishing waste;
- Gaps in the biology and ecology of wild stocks;
- Expedite methodologies for monitoring the status of wild stocks;
- Ecosystem-based management;
- Other topics that can contribute to implementing the CFP and the marine action plan.

3.4. Blue Biotechnology

The European Union's Blue Economy strategy recognizes the vast potential of marine resources to drive sustainable economic growth, innovation, and environmental resilience. As a cornerstone of this strategy, **blue biotechnology**, the application of marine bioresources for industrial, pharmaceutical, and environmental purposes, holds immense promise. Oceans cover over 70% of the Earth's surface and host unparalleled biodiversity, offering novel bioactive compounds, enzymes, and biomaterials that can address global challenges in health, food security, and climate change. The EU's sustainable blue economy framework emphasizes the need for responsible exploitation of marine resources, aligning with the European Green Deal and the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Blue biotechnology can contribute to medicine (e.g., marine-derived antibiotics, anticancer agents, and anti-inflammatory compounds), biodegradable materials (e.g., algae-based plastics, marine collagen), carbon sequestration and bioremediation (e.g., microalgae for CO₂ capture, oil spill degradation), among others. To contribute to the objectives of the AQUASERV Blue Biotechnology call, projects should address one or more of the following topics:

- Discovery and characterization of bioactive compounds from culture collections and biobanks;
- Novel and improved methodologies for sustainable marine bioprospecting;
- Algae biotechnology for food and feed;
- Micro- and macroalgae as protein-rich food alternatives and aquaculture feed supplements;
- Optimization of algal cultivation for high yield and low environmental impact;
- Circular economy approaches for zero-waste marine biomass utilization;
- Further investigate the current Blue Economy narratives underlying the development of economic sectors and Ocean policies (including the use of Marine Spatial Planning) and their consequences on society. Methods should be developed to analyse the future of the Blue Economy across interacting sectors, including how it will adapt at multiple scales (European Marine Board, 2024);
- Other topics that contribute to implementing the CFP and the marine action plan.

4. Conclusions / Next steps

The AQUASERV challenge-driven call and application procedure is similar to the permanent call for generalised topics using the ARIA platform, scientific peer review of the projects using external reviewers, and decision by user selection panel.

The calendar for launching, submission, and announcement of results is the following:

⁷ https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/policy/common-fisheries-policy-cfp/action-plan-protecting-and-restoring-marine-ecosystems-sustainable-and-resilient-fisheries_en#:~:text=The%20European%20Commission%20adopted%20the%20marine%20action%20plan,our%20seas%2C%20with%20one%20third%20being%20strictly%20protected.

⁸ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/biodiversity-strategy-2030_en

Challenge Driven Call	Call Launch	Submission deadline	Results
1. Ecological Restoration	April 2025	August 2025	November 2025
2. Aquaculture	December 2025	March 2026	July 2026
3. Fisheries	July 2026	November 2026	March 2027
4. Blue Economy	April 2027	July 2027	November 2027
5. All 4 topics	December 2027	March 2028	July 2028

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Heip, C. and McDonough, N. (2012). Marine Biodiversity: A Science Roadmap for Europe. Marine Board Future Science Brief 1, European Marine Board, Ostend, Belgium. ISBN: 978-2-918428-75-6.

JPI Oceans Strategy Framework 2021-2025

Review of the Strategic Research Innovation Agenda from the European Aquaculture Technology Innovation Platform (2017)

Frederik Scholaert, lead author, with contributions from Vasileios Margaras, Marketa Pape, Alex Wilson and Clara Antonia Kloecker. The blue economy Overview and EU policy framework. ISBN: 978-92-846-6261-6 DOI:10.2861/253712